

FORMULATION AND IN VITRO EVALUATION OF ETHOSOMAL TRANSDERMAL PATCH OF IRBESARTAN

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ABSTRACT

The present study was aimed at the formulation and in vitro evaluation of ethosomal transdermal patches of Irbesartan, an angiotensin II receptor antagonist widely used in the management of hypertension. Irbesartan suffers from low oral bioavailability (~60–70%) due to extensive first-pass metabolism, making transdermal delivery a promising alternative to improve therapeutic efficacy. Ethosomes, phospholipid-based elastic nanocarriers containing high ethanol content, were employed to enhance drug permeation through the skin. Ethosomal suspensions of Irbesartan were prepared by the cold method and characterized for vesicle size, entrapment efficiency, and zeta potential. Optimized ethosomal formulation was incorporated into a hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) and sodium alginate based transdermal patches using the solvent evaporation technique. The prepared patches were evaluated for physicochemical parameters such as thickness,

weight uniformity, folding endurance, moisture absorption, and drug content. In vitro drug release studies using Franz diffusion cells apparatus. The optimized ethosomal patch exhibited controlled release of Irbesartan over 12 hours with improved permeation and flux values. Stability studies revealed satisfactory physical integrity and drug retention. The findings suggest that ethosomal-based transdermal delivery of Irbesartan offers a novel and effective strategy for improving bioavailability, reducing dosing frequency, and enhancing patient compliance in hypertension management.

KEYWORDS: Ethosomes, Irbesartan, Polymers, Solvent evaporation method, Transdermal patch.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is a major global health burden and a leading cause of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality.^[1] Irbesartan, a poorly water-soluble BCS Class II angiotensin II receptor blocker, exhibits limited oral bioavailability (60–80%) due to poor solubility and first-pass metabolism, requiring high daily doses (75,150 & 300 mg).^[2,3]

Transdermal delivery offers a promising alternative by bypassing hepatic metabolism, providing sustained release, reducing dosing frequency, and improving patient compliance.^[4] However, the stratum corneum significantly restricts drug permeation.^[5] Ethosomes — soft vesicles containing high ethanol content (20–45%) — enhance skin penetration by disrupting lipid bilayers and increasing vesicle deformability, making them superior to conventional liposomes for transdermal delivery.^[6,7]

Incorporating ethosomes into polymeric patches combines enhanced permeation with controlled release, offering a viable strategy for prolonged antihypertensive therapy.^[8,9] The present study aims to formulate and evaluate an ethosomal transdermal patch of irbesartan for improved skin permeation and sustained drug delivery.

NEED OF STUDY

- The Angiotensin II receptor blocker (ARB) Irbesartan has demonstrated a high efficacy in lowering blood pressure, which has been shown to be at least comparable with Angiotensin Converting Enzyme-I and superior to other ARBs such as losartan and valsartan.
- Irbesartan is a BCS class II drug, it has better solubility in ethanol, dose is 75mg once daily, Half life is 11-15hrs, Bioavailability 60-80%, absorbed from the upper part of GIT.
- Irbesartan can be formulated as Ethosomes to improve its solubility and enhance Bioavailability.
- The cost-effectiveness for Irbesartan is better than valsartan and losartan in the treatment of hypertension.
- Irbesartan has low number of drug related adverse effects than other ARBs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

List of Materials

Table 1: List of materials used.

S.No	Material	Manufacturer
1	Irbesartan	Hetero drugs, Hyderabad
2	Phosphotidyl choline	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
3	HPMC	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
4	Sodium alginate	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
5	Ethanol	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
6	DMSO	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
7	Glycerin	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
8	Sodium hydroxide	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
9	Di-sodium hydrogen ortho phosphate	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited
10	Potassium dihydrogen phosphate	SDFCL ,s.d. fine-chem limited

List of Equipments

Table 2: Equipment's used for preparation and analysis.

S No	Equipment	Supplier
1	Digital Weighing machine (sensitivity: 0.001mg)	Sartorius TE 124S
2	Precision balance CB-Series.(sensitivity: 10 mg)	Contech
3	Magnetic stirrer	Aditya scientific
4	Hot Air Oven	Cintex Ind. Corporation
5	UV-Visible Spectrophotometer	Lab India
6	Sonicator (sonica ultrasonic cleaner-2200MH)	Spinotech Pvt. Ltd, India
7	pH Meter	Lab India Sab 5000
8	SEM	XL30, Philips
9	FTIR	Shimaduz
10	Zeta Analyser	Malvern
11	Franz diffusion cell	Malvern

Pre-formulation studies^[10]

Organoleptic Properties

Purpose: Initial physical examination.

Procedure: Observe color, odor, taste, and appearance of the API under normal conditions.

Solubility Studies

Purpose: To check solubility in different solvents and pH conditions.

Known amount of API is Added to various solvents. Shake at constant temperature until equilibrium is reached. Filter and analyze concentration by UV/Vis spectrophotometer.

Melting Point Determination: capillary melting point apparatus is used gradually heated and melting point was noted.

Determination of Drug concentration wavelength and absorbance^[10]

Preparation of pH 7.4 Phosphate Buffer

A phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 was prepared by dissolving 2.48 g of disodium hydrogen phosphate, 0.19 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate, and 8 g of sodium hydroxide in sufficient water and making up the final volume to 1000 mL.

Preparation of Standard Curve of Irbesartan in pH 7.4 Buffer

A stock solution of Irbesartan (1 mg/mL) was prepared by accurately weighing 10 mg of Irbesartan and dissolving it in 10 mL of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. From this stock solution, serial dilutions were made with the same buffer to obtain working standard solutions having concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 µg/mL.

Determination of Standard Curve of Irbesartan in pH 7.4 Buffer

The absorbance of each diluted Irbesartan solution (prepared in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer) was measured using a UV/Visible spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 228 nm. A calibration curve was constructed by plotting absorbance versus concentration.

Drug-Excipient Compatibility Study by FTIR Spectroscopy^[11]

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was performed using a Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer (Prestige-21, Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan). Samples were analyzed by the potassium bromide (KBr) disc method: 1 mg of the test sample was thoroughly mixed with 100 mg of dry KBr powder, the mixture was compressed into a transparent disc using a hydraulic press, and the disc was then placed in the spectrophotometer for scanning across the infrared region.

Formulation development

Table 3: Composition of Irbesartan Ethosomes (F1 to F8).

S.No.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	Irbesartan (mg)	75	75	75	75	75	75	75	75
2	Phosphotidyl choline (mg)	50	75	100	125	150	175	200	225
3	Ethanol (ml)	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
4	Water (ml)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

Procedure

CHARACTERIZATION

Particle size

The particle size of ethosomal gel batches was determined microscopically by measuring the size of ethosomes at different locations on a slide and calculating the average size.^[16]

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Analysis

The surface morphology and structure of the ethosomes were examined using a scanning electron microscope (XL30, Philips, The Netherlands). Prior to imaging, the lyophilized ethosomal samples were sputter-coated with gold under vacuum. Micrographs were captured at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV and a beam current of 750 mA.^[17]

Zeta Potential

The zeta potential of ethosomes was measured using a zeta sizer instrument to determine surface charge, with ideal values ranging from +30 to -30 mV to prevent particle aggregation.^[18]

Formulation development (Transdermal patches)

Table 4: Formulation Design of Irbesartan Ethosomal Transdermal Patches.

Formulation code	Irbesartan Ethosomes (ml)	Sodium alginate (mg) (0.5 %w/v)	HPMC(mg) (0.5 %w/v)	Glycerin (ml)	DMSO (ml) (0.5%v/v)
F1	5	100	-	10	0.10
F2	5	200	-	10	0.10
F3	5	300	-	10	0.10
F4	5	400	-	10	0.10
F5	5	-	100	10	0.10
F6	5	-	200	10	0.10
F7	5	-	300	10	0.10
F8	5	-	400	10	0.10

Preparation of Irbesartan Ethosomal Transdermal Patches

Evaluation of transdermal formulation

Physical Appearance

The prepared transdermal patches were visually evaluated for colour, clarity, flexibility, and surface smoothness.

Folding Endurance

Folding endurance was determined by repeatedly folding each patch at the same point until it broke or showed visible cracks. The number of folds the patch withstood without breaking was recorded, and the mean value was calculated.

Thickness

The thickness of each patch was measured at three different locations using a screw gauge. The average of these measurements was reported as the patch thickness.

Weight Uniformity

Patches were dried at 60 °C for 4 hours. A specified area (4.52 cm²) was cut from each patch and weighed individually on an analytical balance. The average weight and standard deviation were then calculated.

Drug content

Drug content was assayed in triplicate for each formulation, with three patches tested from each to determine the amount of drug present.^[20]

Moisture absorption studies

Moisture uptake was calculated by weighing patches before and after storage in a desiccator with 79.50% RH for 3 days.^[21]

$$\text{Percentage moisture uptake} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

Moisture loss studies

Moisture loss was calculated by weighing patches before and after storage in a desiccator with calcium chloride at 37°C for 24 hours.^[22]

$$\text{Percentage moisture loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Final weight}} \times 100$$

In-vitro Drug release studies

In vitro drug permeation studies were performed using a modified Franz diffusion cell with a receptor compartment capacity of 10 mL. Samples withdrawn from the receptor compartment at predetermined time intervals were analyzed for drug content by UV spectrophotometry.

Percentage Drug Release

The cumulative percentage of drug released at each time point was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ drug release} = \frac{D_t}{D_a} \times 100$$

Where, D_t = Amount of drug released at time t

D_a = Total amount of drug initially incorporated in the patch

Conditions

Medium: Phosphate buffer pH 7.4

RPM: 200

Temperature: $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$

Time intervals: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 hours

Release Kinetics^[23]

The in vitro drug release data were fitted to various kinetic models to determine the mechanism and pattern of drug release.

Zero-Order Kinetics

$$Q_t = K_0 t$$

Where Q_t is the amount of drug released at time t , and K_0 is the zero-order release rate constant (expressed as concentration/time).

First-Order Kinetics

$$\log Q_t = \log Q_0 - (K_1 t)/2.303$$

Where Q_0 is the initial amount of drug, Q_t is the amount of drug remaining at time t , and K_1 is the first-order release rate constant.

Higuchi Model

$$Q_t = K_H t^{(1/2)}$$

Where Q_t is the amount of drug released at time t , and K_H is the Higuchi dissolution constant.

Korsmeyer–Peppas Model

$$M_t / M = KKP t^n$$

Where M_t / M is the fraction of drug released at time t , KKP is the Korsmeyer–Peppas release rate constant, and n is the release exponent indicative of the drug release mechanism.

Stability Studies

The optimized transdermal patches were subjected to accelerated stability testing by storing them at 25 ± 2 °C and $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity (RH) for 3 months. Physical appearance and drug content were evaluated at monthly intervals to assess the stability of the formulation.

RESULTS

Preformulation studies

- Organoleptic evaluation

Table 5: Organoleptic properties of Irbesartan.

Properties	Results
Description	White Crystalline Powder
Taste	Tasteless
Odour	Odourless
Colour	White

Determination of melting point

The melting point of Irbesartan was determined using a capillary melting point apparatus and was found to be in the range of 180–181 °C, which was in close agreement with the reported literature value, thereby confirming the purity and authenticity of the drug sample.

Table 6: Determination of Melting point.

REFERENCE RANGE	OBSERVED RANGE
180-181°C	180°C

Solubility

Table 7: Solubility of Irbesartan in various solvents.

SOLVENTS	SOLUBILITY(mg/ml)
Water	0.009
Methanol	1.284
Ethanol	1.396
DMSO	0.985
DMF	0.871
Phosphate Buffer PH 7.4	0.889
Phosphate Buffer PH 6.8	0.852

Determination of drug absorbance

Preparation of Standard Calibration Curve of Irbesartan

A standard calibration curve for Irbesartan was constructed in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 at λ_{\max} 228 nm. Absorbance of standard solutions (10–50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was plotted against corresponding concentrations. The curve exhibited excellent linearity and obeyed Beer–Lambert’s law over the studied concentration range, with a regression coefficient (R^2) of 0.997.

Fig. 18: Spectrum of Irbesartan.

Table 8: Calibration curve of Irbesartan in 7.4 phosphate buffer.

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Absorbance (nm)
5	0.119 ± 0.010
10	0.280 ± 0.013
15	0.418 ± 0.015
20	0.571 ± 0.014
25	0.745 ± 0.012
30	0.889 ± 0.016

Fig. 19: Calibration curve of Irbesartan.

The wavelength of maximum absorption (λ_{max}) for Irbesartan in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer was confirmed to be 228 nm. A standard calibration curve was prepared over the concentration range of 1–5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The drug exhibited strict adherence to Beer–Lambert’s law within this range, demonstrating excellent linearity.

Table 9: Characteristic Peaks and frequency of Irbesartan.

S.No.	Characteristic Peaks	Frequency range (cm-1)	Frequency (cm-1)
1	OH stretching	4000-3500	3857.76
2	OH Bending	3000-2500	2926.11
3	C-H stretching	2500-2000	2297.30
4	C=O stretching	1500-1000	1383.01

Fig. 20: FT-IR graph for Irbesartan.

Table 10: FTIR Spectra of physical mixture of drug and excipients.

S.No.	Characteristic Peaks	Frequency range (cm-1)	Frequency (cm-1)
1	OH stretching	4000-3500	3857.76
2	OH Bending	3000-2500	2729.19
3	C-H stretching	2500-2000	2335.92
4	C=O stretching	1500-1000	1450.52

SHIMADZU

Fig. 21: FTIR Spectra of physical mixture of drug and excipients.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

Determination of Vesicle Morphology and Size

The morphology of the formulated ethosomes was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). A small aliquot of the ethosomal suspension was placed on a gold-coated copper stub. The sample was rapidly frozen by plunging into liquid nitrogen under vacuum (cryo-fixation), followed by controlled sublimation of surface water at -85°C for 30 minutes. Subsequently, the dried sample was sputter-coated with gold under vacuum. SEM micrographs were then acquired at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV and a stage temperature of -120°C .

Fig-22: Particle size analysis of Optimized formulation of Ethosomes

Fig-23: Zeta potential of Ethosomes

Table 11: Evaluation Studies of particle size and Zeta potential Ethosomes.

F. No	Particle size (nm)	Zeta potential
F1	253	-29
F2	298	-28
F3	348	-31
F4	326	-35
F5	330	-30
F6	275	-33
F7	229	-27
F8	236	-29

Fig-24: SEM Analysis of Ethosomes

Evaluation of patch formulation

Physical Appearance

The prepared transdermal patches exhibited uniform appearance, smooth surface texture, good flexibility, and homogeneity.

Folding Endurance

The folding endurance values ranged from 175 to 189 folds, reflecting excellent mechanical strength and flexibility. Formulations F4, F5, F7, and F8 demonstrated superior endurance (>185 folds), indicating optimal polymer–plasticizer compatibility and enhanced film robustness.

Weight variation and Thickness

Formulation weights ranged from 159 mg to 179 mg, and thickness values ranged from 0.43 mm to 0.56 mm, with variations within acceptable pharmaceutical limits.

Drug content

Drug content was 75.16% to 81.25%. Formulations F5, F7, and F8 had higher drug content (>80%), indicating suitability for consistent therapeutic efficacy.

% Moisture Loss

Moisture loss was between 7.15% (F2) and 8.12% (F3), with lower values indicating better moisture stability.

Moisture absorption

Moisture absorption was 8.17% to 8.71%. Formulations showed moderate hygroscopicity, with slightly higher absorption in F4 and F5 likely due to hydrophilic excipients.

Table 12: Physicochemical evaluation of Irbesartan transdermal patches.

Formulation code	Weight (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Folding endurance	Drug content (%)	% Moisture loss	% Moisture absorption
F1	163 ± 2.12	0.48 ± 0.10	180 ± 2.2	76.93 ± 0.22	7.58 ± 0.16	8.36 ± 0.14
F2	159 ± 2.14	0.49 ± 0.10	179 ± 2.8	78.51 ± 0.23	7.15 ± 0.21	8.49 ± 0.24
F3	167 ± 2.13	0.53 ± 0.10	182 ± 2.4	75.16 ± 0.25	8.12 ± 0.23	8.52 ± 0.21
F4	165 ± 3.14	0.55 ± 0.10	186 ± 3.3	79.52 ± 0.31	7.62 ± 0.32	8.71 ± 0.30
F5	172 ± 3.12	0.47 ± 0.10	189 ± 3.5	80.25 ± 0.34	7.80 ± 0.36	8.69 ± 0.34
F6	179 ± 3.16	0.43 ± 0.10	175 ± 4.1	79.58 ± 0.36	7.69 ± 0.24	8.17 ± 0.23
F7	170 ± 2.05	0.50 ± 0.10	180 ± 2.3	80.39 ± 0.38	7.85 ± 0.16	8.63 ± 0.29
F8	168 ± 2.02	0.56 ± 0.10	187 ± 2.6	81.25 ± 0.29	7.69 ± 0.25	8.45 ± 0.31

Fig. 25: In vitro drug release studies of F1-F8 formulations.***In vitro* release study**

Irbesartan release studies were conducted in phosphate buffer pH 7.4, showing good linearity (correlation coefficient: 0.998). Drug release was influenced by polymer nature and content.

Table 13: *In vitro* drug release profiles of Irbesartan transdermal patches (F1-F8).

Time	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	15.96 ± 0.12	16.54 ± 0.14	17.20 ± 0.23	10.45 ± 0.25	28.60 ± 0.27	28.60 ± 0.34	18.52 ± 0.32	20.10 ± 0.28
2	27.09 ± 0.23	28.65 ± 0.25	29.66 ± 0.34	16.25 ± 0.43	48.25 ± 0.36	38.14 ± 0.34	28.96 ± 0.42	30.25 ± 0.36
3	35.92 ± 0.21	37.05 ± 0.23	38.05 ± 0.36	20.63 ± 0.28	65.52 ± 0.36	45.43 ± 0.26	35.96 ± 0.27	37.05 ± 0.34
4	42.53 ± 0.23	44.92 ± 0.47	45.25 ± 0.25	26.23 ± 0.24	89.90 ± 0.23	67.23 ± 0.28	48.85 ± 0.43	49.96 ± 0.45
6	54.10 ± 0.32	55.94 ± 0.36	56.50 ± 0.28	32.39 ± 0.36	99.30 ± 0.46	85.71 ± 0.27	56.98 ± 0.48	58.93 ± 0.27
8	67.10 ± 0.34	68.69 ± 0.26	69.10 ± 0.24	45.76 ± 0.39	99.58 ± 0.35	99.56 ± 0.32	73.99 ± 0.45	75.64 ± 0.24
10	79.24 ± 0.12	81.34 ± 0.35	71.23 ± 0.32	55.24 ± 0.23	99.79 ± 0.20	99.69 ± 0.24	99.55 ± 0.12	87.87 ± 0.33
12	99.85 ± 0.15	89.90 ± 0.24	79.89 ± 0.26	60.56 ± 0.43	97.83 ± 0.28	99.78 ± 0.20	99.84 ± 0.21	99.98 ± 0.20

Kinetic Modelling of Drug Release

In vitro drug release studies were performed on eight Irbesartan transdermal patch formulations using a modified Franz diffusion cell containing pH 6.8 phosphate buffer as the receptor medium. The cumulative drug release data obtained were fitted to the following mathematical models to elucidate the release mechanism:

Zero-order model: Cumulative percentage drug released vs. time

First-order model: Log percentage drug retained vs. time

Higuchi model: Cumulative percentage drug released vs. square root of time

Korsmeyer–Peppas model: Log cumulative percentage drug released vs. log time

The best-fitting model was determined based on the highest regression coefficient (R^2) value and used to interpret the predominant drug release mechanism.

Table 14: Drug Release Kinetics of Formulation F8.

Time (hrs)	%CDR	SQARE T	LOG T	LOG%CDR	ARA	LOG%ARA
0	0	0	0	0	100	0
1	20.1	1	0	1.303196057	79.9	0
2	30.25	1.41421	0.29103	1.480725379	69.75	0.15051
3	37.05	1.73205	0.45712	1.568788212	62.95	0.23856
4	49.96	2	0.62689	1.69862243	50.04	0.30103
6	58.93	2.44949	0.70815	1.770336441	41.07	0.38908
8	75.64	2.82843	0.91031	1.87875152	24.36	0.45154
10	87.87	3.16228	0.96025	1.943840626	12.13	0.5
12	99.25	3.4641	1.07449	1.996730515	0.75	0.53959

Fig. 26: Zero order kinetics of optimized formulation.

Fig. 27: First order kinetics of optimized formulation.

The formulation F8 followed zero-order release kinetics, and all Irbesartan transdermal patches followed the Korsmeyer-Peppas release mechanism.

Table 15: Regression equations of optimized formulation.

F. No	In vitro release in phosphate buffer PH 6.8			
	Regression values			
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi Plot	Korsmeyer-peppas
F8	0.972	0.549	0.639	0.979

Table 16: Stability studies of optimized formulations at 25 ± 2 °C and 75 ± 5 % RH for 3 months.

Time in days	Drug content (%)	Folding endurance	Physical appearance	% Cumulative drug release
0	81.25	187	No change in color	99.98
90	80.89	186	Slight yellowish color	98.20

Irbesartan release studies used phosphate buffer pH 7.4, showing good linearity ($R^2 = 0.998$). Drug release was influenced by HPMC polymer nature and content.

CONCLUSION

The study aimed to prepare and evaluate ethosomal transdermal patches of Irbesartan to enhance solubility and absorption. The results showed promise for hypertension management using this novel drug delivery system.

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